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EDUCATIONAL CULTURE AND ITS PHILOSOPHICAL FOUNDATIONS: CONCEPTUAL APPROACHES, EPISTEMOLOGICAL ROOTS AND AXIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

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Summary: The article is devoted to the philosophical understanding of the concept of educational culture based on a conceptual paradigm. It analyzes the gnoseological roots of education, the interaction of educational culture with social and cultural factors, and historical pedagogical approaches. Special attention is given to the critical and axiological analysis of existing perspectives on educational culture, with recommendations for their improvement.

Keywords: Educational culture; conceptual paradigm; gnoseological roots; socio-cultural relations; history of pedagogical thought; axiological analysis; critical approach; cultural approach; educational model.

Introduction. As one of the pillars of modern civilization, education is not just a set of knowledge or a set of skills, but a spiritual and cultural phenomenon that sustainably guides human development, spiritually and intellectually improves the individual, and strengthens universal values. Therefore, in today's globalization environment, the concept of "educational culture" is increasingly being mentioned not only in the framework of pedagogy and sociology, but also in the center of philosophical discourses. After all, this concept is understood not as organizational mechanisms or didactic methods of the educational process, but as a system of values, spiritual institutions, cultural traditions, and a general complex of the intellectual environment that determine the moral and spiritual image of society [1;89]. The philosophical essence of educational culture is the formation of the cognitive process not just as an informational stream, but in a spiritual and moral context, that is, as a process of self-awareness, self-discovery, and awareness of one's responsibility in society. As UNESCO experts noted, educational culture is "not just the imparting of knowledge, but the art of directing a person towards critical thinking, creative research, social responsibility and sustainable development" [2;33]. Thus, educational culture is the embodied form of society's own historical memory and ideal vision of the future, a philosophical criterion regulating its spiritual world.

From this perspective, educational culture, on the one hand, is a means of ensuring the spiritual and intellectual development of the individual, and on the other, it manifests itself as a form of self-awareness of society. It transforms not only personal consciousness, but also social consciousness; it not only transmits existing knowledge, but also projects the future. Through educational culture, society re-understands its historical experience, seeks new ways to solve modern problems, and at the same time determines the general spiritual perspective of humanity.

Literature review. The theoretical foundations underlying the culture of education are the product of the consistent evolution of human thought from ancient times to the present. While Plato's doctrine of the "Virtuous Society" interprets education as a high means of directing the soul to beauty and goodness [3], J. Dewey's pragmatic pedagogy interprets it as a process of reproducing educational and social experience, that is, educating a person based on adaptability to the living environment [4]. Although these two views differ from each other, what connects them is the view of education as a phenomenon deeply embedded in the social and cultural context.

Uzbek thinkers have also contributed to this issue with their own unique approaches. In particular, according to Kh. Toshkhodjaev, "educational culture is a social reproduction of intergenerational spiritual heritage, which is not just a system of knowledge, but also the spiritual essence of learning" [5;145]. This definition interprets educational culture not only as a process of knowledge, but also as a spiritual bridge connecting the memory and future of society. If we analyze the practical aspects, it becomes clear that educational culture is a much broader phenomenon than curricula and textbooks. Its main manifestation is manifested in the moral and

cultural relations between the teacher and the student, in how the education system establishes dialogue with society. Also, gender equality, inclusiveness, respect for human rights, the opportunity to freely express opinions and ask critical questions constitute the core criteria of educational culture [6;55]. After all, the level of educational culture is measured not only by the quality of knowledge provision, but also by how it respects human dignity.

In critical philosophical approaches, the views of M. Foucault and P. Bourdieu occupy a special place. Foucault sees education as an institution that produces and distributes power, connecting it with a mechanism of social control and discipline [7;101]. Bourdieu, on the other hand, interprets education as a means of reproducing "cultural capital" and reveals the hidden mechanisms of social stratification in it [8;138]. These views reveal the structural imbalances and inequalities that lie behind the external harmony of educational culture.

It is from this critical perspective that the problems existing in today's educational culture - the limitation of thinking by standardized assessment systems, the encouragement of service to the system rather than the creative potential of the individual, the dominance of approaches that promote obedience instead of freedom - are becoming the most urgent object of philosophical criticism of modern education. Therefore, the task of reshaping the culture of education requires seeing a person not as a part of the system, but as a free thinker, a creative person, and a spiritual being. Therefore, the philosophical essence of the culture of education is not to arm a person with knowledge, but to open him to the deeper meanings of existence, to lead him to self-awareness through creative and critical thinking.

Research methodology. The methodological foundations of this study are based on philosophical-epistemological, sociocultural and critical-theoretical approaches. First of all, the philosophical-epistemological method serves to interpret the culture of education as the formation of the process of human cognition in a spiritual, moral and aesthetic context. This approach is inextricably linked with Plato's ideas about the "pursuit of beauty" and the definitions of spiritual perfection in the teachings of Farabi and Ghazali.

The second aspect is the sociocultural approach, which allows analyzing the culture of education through social institutions, values and cultural capital. This perspective, based on the theory of Pierre Bourdieu, reveals the processes of stratification, inequality and reproduction of education in society. At the same time, the views of Uzbek thinkers on the "intergenerational spiritual heritage" are also used as a methodological basis.

The third methodological direction is the critical-theoretical approach. Michel Foucault's views on the complex relationships between power and knowledge are important in exposing the mechanisms of social control and discipline in educational culture. J. Dewey's pragmatism has also been used to analyze education as a reproduction of social experience.

Analyses and results. In today's era of globalization and technological progress, educational culture is emerging not as a simple pedagogical issue, but as a problem that has acquired a philosophical, sociological and political essence. It represents the dialectical relationship between the individual and society, the intellectual growth and moral stability of man. Therefore, the renewal of educational culture should be carried out not only through reforms or organizational measures, but also through deepening conceptual thinking, expanding scientific dialogue and reassessing the system of values. In this approach, educational culture goes beyond the provision of knowledge and becomes a means of educating humanity and strengthening spiritual harmony in society. The technological revolution of the 21st century is fundamentally affecting the content and forms of education, leading it towards a new cultural paradigm. The widespread use of digital tools is not just a technical innovation, but a turn in the thinking of society. In Manuel Castells's concept of the "information society", educational culture is reinterpreted as the main source of knowledge production. This shows the place of the educational process as a global institution that develops not only the transfer of knowledge, but also spiritual and intellectual capital.

The cultural dimension of digital education is embodied in a person's self-awareness, attitude to knowledge, information literacy and digital ethics. In the context of Uzbekistan, the

“Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy has set this new cultural turn and set as its goal the creation of a modern bridge between knowledge and culture. This strategy aims to transform the culture of education into a central factor of human capital and social development.

At the same time, the principle of inclusion is a priority in modern global education policy. Inclusive education is an approach aimed at creating equal opportunities not only for individuals with disabilities, but also for all marginalized groups - socially, economically and culturally vulnerable groups. In this process, the culture of education must be aligned with a social mindset that values justice, equality, tolerance, and diversity. Within the framework of Martha Nussbaum's "powers approach," education is interpreted as the right of a person to realize his or her potential. Thus, the culture of education is the spiritual foundation of society, the basis of a just social order, and the criterion of humanity. It is not a simple information transmission system, but a force that brings the individual to maturity, harmonizes society, and sustainably develops civilization.

Conclusion. National educational culture is a product of the historical memory, religious and philosophical heritage and social structure of each nation. In the case of Uzbekistan, it is not just a system of imparting knowledge, but also a continuation of the scientific and spiritual heritage created by such scholars as al-Khwarizmi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Al-Farabi and Ulugbek. In their view, education is interpreted as a means leading a person to cosmic harmony, and a force leading society to spiritual perfection. Therefore, modern educational policy should see this heritage not just as a historical monument, but as a source that synthesizes with new cultures and teaches how to live in harmony with global processes. It is not for nothing that special emphasis is placed on renewing the culture of education within the framework of the “New Uzbekistan” concept put forward by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. After all, this process is a conceptual movement aimed at harmonizing with global trends while preserving national values [12;17]. This harmony means keeping up with the times without losing national identity.

In today's era of globalization, digital sociality and cultural conflicts, educational culture is not just a collection of scientific knowledge. It is a form of consciousness that projects the future, a mechanism for educating a well-rounded individual who can solve global problems of humanity. Only education based on human criteria, not just technological innovations or organizational reforms, will give real results. Because if human dignity, moral excellence and scientific thinking are not a priority in the educational process, then the effectiveness of reforms will remain superficial. Therefore, the process of developing educational culture must always be based on three pillars - social justice, moral purity and scientific thinking. Only then can it become a cultural foundation that harmonizes national and universal values, leading humanity to spiritual perfection and future stability.

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Rezyume: Ushbu maqola ta'lim madaniyati tushunchasini konseptual paradigmalar asosida falsafiy talqin qiladi. Unda ta'lim madaniyatining gnoseologik ildizlari, shaxs va jamiyat o'rtasidagi ijtimoiy-madaniy aloqalar tahlil qilinadi. Mualliflar pedagogik fikr tarixida shakllangan yondashuvlarni falsafiy kontekstda o'rganib, zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida madaniy yondashuvning o'rni va ahamiyatini ko'rsatadilar. Shuningdek, ta'lim madaniyatiga oid mavjud nazariy qarashlar aksiologik va tanqidiy tahlil qilinib, ularni takomillashtirish bo'yicha falsafiy tavsiyalar beriladi.

Резюме: Статья посвящена философскому осмыслению понятия образовательной культуры на основе концептуальной парадигмы. Анализируются гносеологические корни образования, взаимодействие образовательной культуры с социальными и культурными факторами, а также исторические педагогические подходы. Особое внимание уделяется критическому и аксиологическому анализу существующих взглядов на образовательную культуру и предложению рекомендаций по их совершенствованию.

Kalit so'zlar: Ta'lim madaniyati; konseptual paradigma; gnoseologik ildizlar; ijtimoiy-madaniy aloqalar; pedagogik fikr tarixi; aksiologik tahlil; tanqidiy yondashuv; madaniy yondashuv; ta'lim modeli.

Ключевые слова: Культура образования; концептуальная парадигма; гносеологические корни; социально-культурные связи; история педагогической мысли; аксиологический анализ; критический подход; культурный подход; образовательная модель.